

WP 5

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MUSES Project

Title: Exploitation of Results Plan

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1. Introduction and Background

The purpose of the Exploitation of Results Plan (“ERP”) is to ensure that the project’s aims, progress and results are exploited and disseminated effectively to those directly involved in marine spatial planning and multiple uses of the oceans, as well as being easily accessible to a wider audience. This document has been created under deliverable 5.12 (due at the end of Month 12) of Work Package 5 and will be revisited and updated as required under deliverable 5.13 in month 24 at the end of the project. This document will be publicly available on the MUSES website.

Dissemination and exploitation of results is an integral part of the MUSES approach. The ERP is based on the following pillars:

- **Engagement of key actors**: stakeholder engagement is the backbone of MUSES project, and will underpin the advancement in multi-use (“MU”) implementation. Our approach to stakeholder engagement will be multi-level (international, EU, Sea Basins, national, local), multi-sector (involving stakeholders from different marine and maritime uses) and will mobilise actors involved at different steps in the process of MU (actors from policy, legislative, administrative, financial, environmental). We have established a database of stakeholders, which will be continuously updated throughout the course of the project. This will be used to effectively focus different stakeholder events, target groups for dissemination and organize stakeholder feedback throughout the course of the project and beyond.
- **Clear communication strategy**: The ERP is aimed at informing the general public, media, stakeholders from marine and maritime sectors, and organizations and public authorities interested in maritime activities and outcomes of the project. This ERP follows the communication guidelines recommended by the EC, and involves a diversity of actors and promote social support (not only social acceptance) of MU. Moreover, MUSES has developed web-based communication tools, which will integrate different channels and includes:
 1. web information portal to provide access to project progress, documentation and MU newsletter, and more generally serve as a MU information platform.
 2. web-dialogue platform for stakeholders’ involvement, including links to social media communication tools and ability to comment on case study progress via the website.
- **Knowledge management**: all publications and reports (with the exception of consortium only deliverables) arising from MUSES are being made available to the public either through self-archiving (for technical reports, progress

reports, non-peer reviewed literature) or will be available through open access facilities (for peer-reviewed publications).

- **Dissemination of results:** MUSES will promote concrete advances in MU development, at regional and local levels, using case studies to produce practical progress in MU and co-existence. An action plan will be developed under work package 4 to feed into national, macro-regional, sea basin and EU policy processes, through mechanisms established within our stakeholder engagement activities. Mechanisms are being implemented to disseminate project results, including regular updates on the MUSES website, social media presence, newsletters, project flyers, press releases, project publications, project infographics, attendance at conferences and holding workshops.

2. *EU Rules for Dissemination and Protection of Results*

2.1 *Dissemination of Results, Open Access and Visibility of EU Funding* Dissemination Requirements

Project partners must promote the actions and results of the project by providing targeted information to multiple audiences in a strategic and effective manner. **All communications and publications must comply with European Commission rules for dissemination as set down in the Grant Agreement (Art. 38).**

Open Access

Under Article 29.3 of the Grant Agreement, each partner must ensure free of charge online access for any user (“open access”) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, they must:

(a) as soon as possible, and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications. Moreover, the partner must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

(b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:

- (i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
- (ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

Visibility of EU Funding

Any Communication activity relating to the action (including in electronic form, via social media) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

(a) Display the EU Emblem on all outputs. (when displayed with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence)

(b) Include the following text:

‘This Project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 727451’

Project partners may use the EU Emblem to promote MUSES action and results without first obtaining approval from INEA; however, this does not give the right to exclusive use.

This project has received funding
from the European Union’s Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement no 727451

Figure 1 – EU emblem & text requirement

2.2 Protection of Results

Each partner must examine the possibility of protecting its results and must take measures to adequately protect them. This should be done for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage especially if the results can be reasonably expected to be commercially or industrially exploited and protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified (given the circumstances).

When deciding on protection, each partner must consider its own legitimate interests and the legitimate interests (especially commercial) of the other partners.

If a partner intends not to protect its results, to stop protecting them or not seek an extension of protection, the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (“INEA”) may — under certain conditions (Article 26.4) — assume ownership to ensure their (continued) protection.

3. Dissemination Activities

The following methods are in place, or will be developed, to maximise the impact of the Project results by ensuring that the Project aims, progress and results are disseminated effectively to those interested in MU of our oceans. This is a vital aspect of the Project and work package 5 is a distinct work stream that deals with engagement, communication and dissemination.

The dissemination process comprises of discrete but interrelated strands to ensure that MUSES reaches the widest possible audience of European stakeholders. Marine Scotland are co-ordinating the dissemination process, with Project Partners communicating the results of the Project to their own country and through their own networks to achieve maximum impact in Europe and potentially beyond.

The following activities have been undertaken in the first year of the project to achieve dissemination goals for the project and to begin exploitation of the results achieved to date.

3.1 Project Logo

A project logo was developed by designers at The Gaspar Frutuoso Foundation. The MUSES logo is embedded on the Project website, and is embedded in the Project Twitter feed. Partners are required to use this logo within all dissemination activities.

Figure 2 – MUSES Logo

3.2 Templates

Templates have been created for partners to use in order to disseminate progress, results and updates to stakeholders. These templates include reports, posters and presentations. The templates are stored on the project SharePoint site and partners are required to use these templates throughout the course of the project.

3.3 Infographics

Marine Scotland has developed an initial infographic at month 3 under Work Package 5 which is used to promote the Project through various media, a further infographic will be developed under this WP as results emerge from the project. Further infographics will also be developed for the Project under Work Package 3 which will focus on case studies at month 14. If sufficient resources are available, additional infographics may be produced to assist with the exploitation of results obtained from the project.

Figure 3 – 1st Infographic

3.4 Project Leaflets

A MUSES leaflet has been developed and produced and is available to view on the project website. The leaflet contains Project information and Project objectives, for the purposes of promoting the Project, gathering interest and directing people to visit

the Project website and sign up for the mailing list. It also contains the first of the project's infographics. These leaflets are particularly useful for promotional purposes when attending events and are made available at conferences and exhibitions where Project Partners have a presence.

3.5 Project Website

The Project website is the outward facing platform for the MUSES Project and provides a platform for effective dissemination of Project activities, updates to stakeholders and to exploit the results of the project by providing open access to this. The website also acts as a communications platform for stakeholders to comment on the results of the project and engage in discussions.

The project website is being managed by Marine Scotland and is hosted by the University of Dundee. All MUSES team members are encouraged to collaborate on periodical updating of the website and can do so by forwarding material to Marine Scotland for publication. The website can be found at : <http://muses-project.eu>

3.6 Social Media

A social media presence has been established through Twitter and LinkedIn. Marine Scotland is responsible for maintaining this presence by promoting MUSES news and information from the project. Marine Scotland shall be primarily responsible for the dissemination of information through social media. Partners are encouraged to share MUSES information through their own social media platform in order to reach as large an audience as possible. However, any information not previously shared via the official MUSES platforms must first be approved by Marine Scotland. This will also allow any other information to be shared via the MUSES platforms.

3.7 Newsletters

The purpose of newsletters is to disseminate project updates and high level results from workshops and work-streams by electronic means to stakeholders. Under work package 5 a total of at least 5 electronic newsletters will be produced and disseminated by Marine Scotland throughout the lifetime of the Project and will correspond to significant events/deliverables. At the half way stage of the project 3 newsletters have been sent out to stakeholders.

The newsletter service is being produced through the MailChimp online service. Stakeholders who have been interviewed by project partners under work packages 2 and 3 are asked if they wish to be added to the mailing list. Stakeholders who the Project team have an e-mail address for have been sent a MUSES newsletter 'opt-in' e-mail. The Project website also has a sign up option. A complete list of stakeholders who sign up for a Newsletter is saved through MailChimp and a separate back-up list maintained by Marine Scotland.

Downloadable versions of previous newsletters are kept on the website.

3.8 MUSES Promotion at Events

MUSES will be represented at, provide Project presentations and/or take stands at a minimum of 16 events. During the first half of the project, MUSES has been represented at 10 events across Europe. Partners are required to register these attendances on the online events register kept on the MUSES SharePoint site.

Deliverable D5.5 – MUSES attendance at a minimum of 16 events

No	Date	Event	Country	Who attended (MUSES partners)	Activity (e.g. presentation, conference stand, dissemination of project information etc)
1	2-3 March 2017	11th meeting of the Member State Expert Group on Maritime Spatial Planning (MSEG)	Germany	Andronikos Kafas	Presentation on the MUSES Project
2	15-17 March 2017	Marine/Maritime Spatial Planning Conference	France	Ivana Lukic	e-Poster presentation
3	3-8 April 2017	ICES working group on Marine Planning and Coastal Zone Management Annual Science Meeting 2017	Spain	Andronikos Kafas	Overview of MUSES to ICES delegates
4	24-28 April 2017	International Conference Maritime Spatial Planning, Ecosystem Approach and Supporting Information Systems (MaPSIS)	Spain	Helena Calado	Workshop to disseminate, discuss and validate, for the Atlantic sea basin, parts of the Analytical Framework
5	10-11 May 2017	All-Energy 2017	Scotland	Tim Roberts, Bruce Buchanan	e-Poster presentation, leaflet distribution, part of Marine Scotland exhibition
6	18-19 May 2017	European Maritime Day	England	Tim Roberts, Bruce Buchanan, Marja Lazic, Andronikos Kafas	Leaflet distribution, networking with potential stakeholders
7	21 st June 2017	Sea Scotland 2017	Scotland	Timothy Roberts	Leaflet distribution, networking with potential stakeholders
8	12-14 July 2017	A New Era of Blue Enlightenment	Portugal	Helena Calado	Presentation
9	12-13 September 2017	Scot Renewables Marine Conference, Inverness	Scotland	Bruce Buchanan	e-Poster presentation, leaflet distribution, part of Marine Scotland exhibition
10	27 th – 28 th September	SUBMARINER – Better off Blue Event	Germany	Majority of partners	Leaflet distribution, presentations
11	5 th October 2017	MASTS Annual Science Meeting	Scotland	Timothy Roberts	e-poster presentation and promotion, leaflet distribution

Table 1 – MUSES Attendance at Events

3.9 Press Releases

A press release was disseminated at the beginning of the MUSES Project and can be found at the attached link and on the MUSES SharePoint. Partners also made press releases through their own channels. Marine Scotland will prepare press releases in advance of workshops/events and will co-ordinate media to maximise interest in relation to the final conference. <https://blogs.gov.scot/marine-scotland/2016/12/07/musing-the-multi-uses-in-european-seas/>

Further press releases, in the form of news updates, have been made on the project website to coincide with key events & activities to serve as a way of updating stakeholders. A final press release will be made to promote the projects final conference.

3.10 Development & Submission of Articles for Academic Journals

The project will generate at least 7 academic papers to peer reviewed journals.

3.11 Project Workshops

The MUSES project held a Stakeholder Engagement Workshop in Poole in May 2017. This was a deliverable under work package 2. The purpose of the workshop was to engage with stakeholders in order to discuss and verify findings on existing MU combinations identified from previous MU projects, developing understanding of the definition of MU concept, as well as clarify the important roles for MU development.

The workshop report is available to view online at the MUSES website and presents the review of findings and outcomes. The report also provides information relating to the establishment of the workshop, reflects on achievements and concludes with recommendations arising from the work of the participants.

A second stakeholder workshop is in the early stages of planning, but may take place in Venice, following the 5th project steering group meeting, due to take place in June 2018. Updates will be provided to potential stakeholders on our website and via other communication channels such as social media.

3.12 Final Project Conference

The final Project conference will be organised in Brussels, which is specifically targeted at EU policy makers in the European Commission, Parliament and institutions. The conference will allow for the presentation of the Project results and recommendations included in MUSES Action Plan with opportunity for discussion and questions. As well as representations from Project Partners, consideration will be given to inviting key experts that have participated in the Project.

MUSES team members will also contribute, upon invitation by the INEA, to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between H2020 supported actions throughout the Project.

3.13 Data Management Plan (DMP)

A DMP has been developed for consortium use to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by MUSES. This document outlines how data is to be handled both during the MUSES project and after the project is completed.

The DMP describes the data management life cycle for all the datasets collected, processed or generated during the project. The aim of the DMP is to improve and maximise access to, and re-use of, research data generated by the MUSES project. The DMP includes:

- the nature of the data that will be generated during the project
- whether and how it will be made accessible (this may vary across work packages depending on the nature of the data), and;
- how it will be maintained and preserved.

3.14 Establishing Links with Other Relevant Projects

The MUSES project aims to build on outcomes from other EU projects related to MU development. Establishing connections with these projects will not only enable MUSES to expand upon and develop these results, but will also create synergies between MUSES and other projects which will allow for dissemination of the results with relevant stakeholders. MUSES also aims to establish links with up-coming EU projects in order to establish links with them to ensure they are aware of the results available from MUSES at an early stage.

In all instances our stakeholder analysis and work will take into account the stakeholder lists developed in past and parallel projects avoiding duplication while at the same time building on “experienced” stakeholders. The MUSES consortium is very well placed to conduct this work, being a unique combination of organisations with complementary skills, including government agencies, networks, natural science research institutes and legal advisors.

4. Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement forms the backbone of the MUSES Project. Stakeholders will fall into two main categories;

- I. those we aim to involve directly in the project to gain from their knowledge and expertise. Stakeholders that are *proactive* in their engagement with MUSES will be engaged in the development of the action plan under WP4. In some cases, where MU is already implemented, stakeholders that have been involved in the facilitation of MU will be considered as *reactive*
- II. the wider audience which is our communication/dissemination target. These are stakeholders are considered “dormant” and are the intended target for the action plan.

These categories are informed by 4 additional attributes that determine at what level stakeholders are engaged at (Table 2): geographical scale at which stakeholder has the power, their organisation (strong clustering, dispersion, etc.), type and, level of power. The strength of priority for each attribute is displayed via the shade of colour in the table (darker colour = higher priority) and this in turn determines the method of engagement for that stakeholder. Those stakeholders that are framed in grey are given the highest priority.

OFFSHORE WIND	Geographical scale at which certain stakeholder has the power	Organisation of stakeholders	Type of power	Level of Power
Commercial Business	Local/regional	couple of individual organisations	Power to influence indirectly	low
Research organisations	National	strong clustering	power to influence directly	low
Regulators	Sea Basin	monopoly of one organisation	power to control and make decisions	strong
Policy makers	Sea Basin	Government departments	power to control and make decisions	strong
Insurance companies	National	couple of individual organisations	power to influence directly	medium
Funding bodies	National	couple of individual organisations	power to influence directly	medium
NGOs/society at large	EU	couple of individual organisations	power to influence directly	medium

Table 2: Example of stakeholder development matrix. Darker colours represent priority engagement factors

The means of engagement will be further developed in the next steps of the project. Figure 4 shows an example of this development.

Figure 4 Power Interest Matrix example (source: mindtools.com)

The location where a stakeholder is placed on the grid identifies what the actions are that MUSES should consider for engagement. For instance:

- High power, interested stakeholders – stakeholders to be fully engaged and should be kept satisfied;
- High power, less interested stakeholders - enough work to keep them satisfied, but not so much that they become bored;
- Low power, interested stakeholders – Helpful stakeholders for project, they should be adequately informed, and consulted for major issues;
- Low power, less interested people: keeping them informed on lower basis.

Interaction with stakeholders is an integral part of WPs 2, 3, 4 & 5 and, as the work has advanced, stakeholders are being engaged in discussion and debate via workshops, interviews and at conferences & events. Stakeholders are being involved from different sectors, with different roles in the MU and maritime spatial planning processes and from different geographic scales (national, sea basin and EU wide) covering all 5 EU sea basins.

Partners should bear in mind that it is important when communicating with stakeholders and the public in general, that this contributes to the efficiency of the participative process. In accordance to some basic communication rules, messages should be delivered in a positive, easy to understand, memorable, accurate and realistic manner. This is achieved by:

- Using language that everyone can understand; maintain simple information; do not try to explain everything;
- Making information interesting; try to associate the information you want to impart to things that people can identify with in their everyday life, using analogies and comparisons;
- Presenting positive elements; do not present only the problems but also possible solutions;
- Knowing the context; put yourself in the other person's shoes; try to be aware of their concerns, interest and knowledge level in relation to the discussion issues; make questions and listen carefully to their concerns;
- Using different methods to transmit the same message;
- Keeping in mind that people retain more information from what they experience rather than from what they simply hear.

4.1 Stakeholder Database

The MUSES project has created a detailed stakeholder database which has been populated via input by all partners. This database will continue to be updated and added to as the project progresses. Stakeholders are classified by their level of engagement with the project and the method of dissemination to them will be

employed appropriately. Due to data protection policies, the database will remain a consortium-only document.

5. *Accessibility & Diversity*

Partners must ensure that reasonable efforts are made to disseminate information in such a way as to be accessible to stakeholders, taking into consideration any additional needs which they may have. This should include, but is not limited to:

- consideration of font, text size, layout and colour
- physical accessibility of conferences
- allowing adequate time for feedback where appropriate
- ensuring alternative formats are available on request
- appropriate use of language
- consideration of non-digital connectivity in stakeholder groups

